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Report on deliverable D4.4: Bibliography of publications using INFRAFRONTIER resources

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1. Executive Summary

A bibliography of scientific publications is a powerful metric on evaluating the impact of the INFRAFRONTIER RI on biomedical research by demonstrating the wide spread use and diverse types of research supported by INFRAFRONTIER. For this deliverable, we created an online bibliography of scientific publications that are related to INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA strains. A two-step approach was taken to populate this bibliography. We first built a potential corpus of literature by searching all mouse alleles provided to researchers from INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA nodes in a highly annotated resource maintained by the Jackson Laboratory. We then performed a validation step by creating and using a publication curation tool that facilitated decision making by INFRAFRONTIER personnel on whether a publication should be included based on an established set of criteria. At release the validated bibliography contained 2451 publications and is made available on the INFRAFRONTIER portal where users can search by gene, title, disease or other terms as well as sort publications by date, disease or impact score. The created infrastructure continues to text-mine the scientific literature, allowing the growth of the INFRAFRONTIER bibliography as new scientific papers are published.

2. Introduction

To evaluate the impact of the INFRAFRONTIER RI on biomedical research, we built a database of scientific publications that were potentially been made possible by distribution of INFRAFRONTIER mouse mutant resources. Such a bibliography allows consortium members to better understand the research areas where INFRAFRONTIER resources are being used. Bibliographies also save resources and promotes the three R's by helping researchers avoid duplication of efforts and improve reproducibility of experiments. For example, researchers can quickly find published research that has already been performed with a mutant mouse line and develop their research plan accordingly. At the start of the project, INFRAFRONTIER had a bibliography containing consortium publications, as well as publications cited by submitters as describing creation of a mutant mouse line. Neither of these collections were searchable. For this deliverable we annotated them and developed a public search interface. Most importantly, we expanded this bibliography to include publications validated as describing research that employed INFRAFRONTIER resources (e.g. mouse lines distributed by INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA).

3. Building an INFRAFRONTIER Corpus

To initiate the bibliography, we first created a list of all publications associated with a mutant mouse allele that was distributed by INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA. We considered all mouse alleles provided to researchers by all INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA nodes since the inception of the European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA). We then searched for

publications describing those alleles, as captured by Mouse Genome Informatics curators at the Jackson Laboratory, whom have curated the scientific literature for over 20 years. Using their MouseMine interface [<http://www.mousemine.org>], we retrieved 19,310 papers published in 573 different journals and describing 1,437 alleles. These publications constitute the potential corpus of literature made possible by INFRAFRONTIER.

Figure 1: Building the potential INFRAFRONTIER Corpus

4. Validating the INFRAFRONTIER Bibliography

In the previous step, we identified almost 20,000 publications associated to mutant mouse lines that were possibly distributed by INFRAFRONTIER. Our next step was to validate these publications as actually using resources provided by INFRAFRONTIER. We faced several challenges in doing this. Researchers will often cite a mutant mouse line but not where these were obtained from. While INFRAFRONTIER is the largest distributor of academic mouse lines in Europe, there are other repositories distributing some of the same lines and it cannot be assumed from where they were obtained. Also, researchers will often share lines within and across institutes, adding to the complexity in tracing their source. For these reasons we decided to validate publications to create a gold-standard bibliography. Validation was broken down into several sub-tasks:

Figure 2: Sub tasks to validate the INFRAFRONTIER Bibliography

The first sub-task was to cross reference publications in the potential corpus with those publications cited by archive managers at EMMA nodes as using INFRAFRONTIER resources. This comes from some node’s own curation efforts and added around 220 publications. A second source of publications are the researchers describing a mutant mouse line when depositing the line for distribution by INFRAFRONTIER, which added about 2150. The last set was to manually validate alleles generated by the EUCOMM project associated with 250 publications. This subset of alleles was selected as they were generated and widely distributed in Europe as part of the EC funded EUCOMM and EUCOMMTOOLS projects, thus increasing the likelihood the mouse lines carrying them were distributed by INFRAFRONTIER.

We initiated a manual review process where for each publication, a trained curator would text-search for EMMA and INFRAFRONTIER and ideally for the EMMA ID indicating the mutant strain. If not found, the Methods, Acknowledgements and References sections would be scanned for mentions of the same. If this did not succeed, the curator would then look in supplementary information. While laborious, this approach identified 60 publications describing research using INFRAFRONTIER resources.

Figure 3: Results from manual validation of 250 publications with EUCOMM alleles

An additional 78 publications were labelled as “Maybe” as several elements indicated that mice used might have been obtained from INFRAFRONTIER, but no definitive indication was given. For publications noted as “Maybe” the corresponding author was contacted via email to ask if the research described used INFRAFRONTIER resources with 23 replying in the positive.

During this pilot, the curator noted that manually scanning for required information was time-consuming and could be made more efficient with an appropriate software tool that text mined for trigger words. Working with a software developer, such a tool was designed, implemented and tested using text from 35.5 million abstracts and 5.3 million full text articles as supplied by the EC supported EuroPMC resource. This “Publications Curation Tool” extracts crucial information about the corresponding laboratory, the context in which the mouse allele appears in the manuscript, and the presence of ‘trigger’ words such as “EMMA” that increase the likelihood the publication is describing research using INFRAFRONTIER resources. This resource can be viewed in Figure 4 and at the following URL:

<http://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/mi/infrafrontier/publications/#/>

Trigger words in context of article

Figure 4: Screenshot of the Publications Curation Tool

Based on the experience gathered during the pilot, the Publications Curation Tool will be further refined so that it will be possible to regularly re-run the analysis with much less effort. This will be crucial for keeping the bibliography up-to-date.

5. Disseminating the INFRAFRONTIER Bibliography

As explained above, EBI with the help of EMMA archive managers, curators and the INFRAFRONTIER coordination office built a database of scientific publications that have potentially been made possible by distribution of INFRAFRONTIER mouse mutant resources.

Based on this work INFRAFRONTIER IT in Munich has set up a dynamic bibliography page on the web portal, that lists publications related to EMMA strains. These publications were either provided during strain submission or were confirmed to have been enabled by EMMA distribution.

The URL for the new page is www.infrafrontier.eu/infrafrontier-bibliography. The chart at the top of the bibliography page shows the cumulated number of publications and the publication year (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Chart showing cumulated number of publications and the publication year

The next section lists the publications that are related to EMMA strains (see Figure 6). To provide information on title, abstract, authors, MeSH terms etc. the corresponding data was extracted from PubMed and is regularly updated. We also highlight publications related to strains that carry mutations in genes that are relevant for Rare Diseases.

Showing 1 to 10 of 2,618 entries

First Previous **1** 2 3 4 5 ... 262 Next Last

Cross-species genomics identifies DLG2 as a tumor suppressor in osteosarcoma.
 Oncogene; 2019
 Shao Yang W, Wood Geoffrey A, Lu Jinchang, Tang Qing-Lian, Liu Jonathan, Molyneux Sam, Chen Yan, Fang Hui, Adissu Hibret, McKee Trevor et al
 Abstract
 PMID: 30093633
 EMMA strain(s): C57BL/6N-A<tm1Brd> Dlg2<tm1a(EUCOMM)Wtsi>/Wtsi
 These strains were requested for this publication.

Apobec1 complementation factor (A1CF) and RBM47 interact in tissue-specific regulation of C to U RNA editing in mouse intestine and liver.
 RNA (New York, N.Y.); 2019
 Blanc Valerie, Xie Yan, Kennedy Susan, Riordan Jesse D, Rubin Deborah C, Madison Blair B, Mills Jason C, Nadeau Joseph H, Davidson Nicholas O
 Abstract
 PMID: 30309881
 EMMA strain(s): C57BL/6N-A<tm1Brd> Rbm47<tm1a(EUCOMM)Wtsi>/WtsiBiat
 These strains were requested for this publication.

The deubiquitinase ubiquitin-specific protease 20 is a positive modulator of myocardial β 1-adrenergic receptor expression and signaling.
 The Journal of biological chemistry; 2019
 Yu Samuel Mon-Wei, Jean-Charles Pierre-Yves, Abraham Dennis M, Kaur Suneet, Gareri Clarice, Mao Lan, Rockman Howard A, Shenoy Sudha K
 Abstract
 PMID: 30538132
 EMMA strain(s): C57BL/6NTac-Usp20<tm1a(EUCOMM)Hmgu>/Wtsi
 These strains were requested for this publication.

Smc3 is required for mouse embryonic and adult hematopoiesis.
 Experimental hematology; 2019
 Wang Tianjiao, Glover Brandi, Hadwiger Gayla, Miller Christopher A, di Martino Orsola, Welch John S
 Abstract
 PMID: 30553776
 EMMA strain(s): B6Dnk;B6Brd;B6N-Tyr<c-Brd> Smc3<tm1a(EUCOMM)Wtsi>/WtsiH
 Rare diseases: Cornelia de Lange syndrome
 These strains were requested for this publication.

An atlas of genetic influences on osteoporosis in humans and mice.
 Nature genetics; 2019
 Morris John A, Kemp John P, Youlten Scott E, Laurent Laetitia, Logan John G, Chai Ryan C, Vulpescu Nicholas A, Forgetta Vincenzo, Kleinman Aaron, Mohanty Sindhu T et al
 Abstract
 PMID: 30598549
 EMMA strain(s): C57BL/6N-A<tm1Brd> Daam2<tm1a(KOMP)Wtsi>/WtsiBiat
 These strains were requested for this publication.

Figure 6: Extract of publication list

The default sorting order lists the most recent publication at the top. Clicking on the “Sort by impact” button (see Figure 7) will place publications in high-ranking journals at the top of the table. This is based on Scimago journal ranking data that is regularly updated from <https://www.scimagojr.com>.

A “Filter by rare disease” button allows the user to filter for publications which are related to a Rare Disease (via the linked EMMA strain and the gene that is mutated).

Figure 7: Top navigation bar including sort buttons, search field and pagination

Together with the search box that allows to search for keywords in various fields (EMMA strain related, MeSH term based, disease related, publication related) this provides a powerful tool for INFRAFRONTIER partners to identify impressive examples of INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA’s impact that they can use in presentations. If e.g. CNR Monterotondo wanted to give an example of how INFRAFRONTIER and the Italian EMMA node helped the osteoarthritis field, the search below would pull out a 2014 Cell paper that was published by an EMMA user who received C57BL/6NTac-Slc39a8<tm1a(EUCOMM)Wtsi>/Cnrm mice in 2011 (see Figure 8).

Figure 8: Example of how filter and search features can be used to identify publications that demonstrate impact in a certain discipline with a certain partner’s contribution

The links “submission” and “request” will guide the user to smaller sets of publications either only showing publications provided during strain submission or the publications that were published by INFRAFRONTIER users who received mouse strains from EMMA. This latter set of publications that have been confirmed to have been enabled by EMMA distribution comprised 288 references and EBI and the INFRAFRONTIER GmbH continue to work on adding to the list (see Figure 9).

The INFRAFRONTIER bibliography displays all publications which were provided either during a mutant strain [request](#) or enabled by a mutant strain [submission](#). The chart at the top shows the amount of publications by publication year. The collection below contains detailed information regarding publications linked to INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA¹ strains. The content of the publications was extracted from PubMed². Additionally, we provide the information to linked EMMA strains, MeSH³ terms and rare diseases extracted from the Orphanet⁴ database. The table offers several functionalities to sort, filter and download the table. The table can be sorted by publication year, journal impact factor and related rare diseases. Therefore, the impact factor was extracted from Scimago Journal & Country Rank⁵.

Figure 9: Links in the introductory text to specify the subsets of publications

Finally, all the main external resources used on the bibliography page are

- EBI ontology lookup service
- PubMed
- MeSH
- Ensembl
- Orphanet

6. Perspectives

We describe here the successful delivery of a rich, well annotated INFRAFRONTIER bibliography. This bibliography is now well placed to inform internal strategy of the consortium through better understanding of how resources are being used as well as outreach efforts where the INFRAFRONTIER communications group can highlight INFRAFRONTIER resources being used in high-impact scientific publications. Critically, the INFRAFRONTIER bibliography is not a static resource. The infrastructure created for this deliverable allows for continuing review of the literature for new additions to the bibliography.